

SECTION OF HUMANITIES AND PHILOLOGY

THE ENRICHED AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE THROUGH DIALECT WORDS

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Abstract

Dialectal words are lexical units characterized by their deviation from the norms of literary language, instead being integral to the colloquial language spoken by the local population in a specific geographical region. The presence of these units suggests that the distinction between words in dialects and those in the literary language is not entirely defined. The continual coexistence of literary language and dialects engenders a reciprocal process of lexical enrichment. On the one hand, the literary language selectively incorporates essential and relevant words from dialects into its vocabulary, thereby augmenting its linguistic reservoir. On the other hand, the norms and standards inherent in literary language permeate local dialects and can lead to their suppression. As a result of this, the process of gradual disappearance of dialects and the generalization of the literary language takes place.

Keywords: language, dialect, lexicon, Ganja, term.

The evolution and vitality of a language closely intertwine with societal development. The augmentation of the literary language results from a multitude of sources, and one such source of lexical enrichment is the dialectal lexicon. "Dialects serve as the tangible foundation of the literary language, providing it with sustenance, and they remain an integral part of the language system" [14, p.187]. Dialects are the genuine spoken forms of language among different communities, effectively functioning as linguistic records of those people. The study of dialects allows us to delve into the lives of these people and understand their historical backgrounds.

Dialectal words represent lexical units that do not adhere to the norms of literary language and are employed within the local colloquial discourse of a specific regional population. The presence of these lexical elements suggests that the demarcation between dialectal vocabulary and standard literary language is not definitively established. V.V.Vinogradov, in his exploration of the interplay between literary language and dialects, contends that "the boundaries between accentual vocabulary and the vocabulary of literary language have not received sufficient scholarly attention. Moreover, the mechanisms underlying the incorporation of widely used, vibrant spoken language expressions into formal literary language remain undetermined" [16, p.214]. T.C. Kogotovka supports the same notion and states; "Mundane spoken language and the boundaries of processing of dialect words have not yet been sufficiently studied." Nonetheless, in the development of a national literary language, certain words make a transition from dialects to formal literary language, while conversely, some move from literary language to dialects. Observations reveal that dialectal words, each serving distinct stylistic functions, have found their way into the realm of the literary-artistic language, particularly in modern times.

The constant coexistence of literary language and dialects ensures a reciprocal enrichment of their vocabularies. On one hand, literary language selectively incorporates essential and vibrant words from dialects, thereby enhancing its lexicon. On the other hand, the conventions of literary language infiltrate local dialects and exert an assimilating influence. This leads to a gradual disappearance of dialects and a convergence towards a more generalized literary language.

When discussing the development and enrichment of dialectical elements within the literary language, it is crucial to emphasize that these lexical units are primarily associated with the stylistic dimension of the literary language, particularly in its artistic form. Dialectal vocabulary serves as a foundational resource, significantly benefiting the artistic style of the literary language. This is because dialect words predominantly find their way into the literary language through creative works. As articulated by the following passage: "In the assimilation of dialecticisms into the lexicon of the literary language, the realm of fiction assumes a transitional role. Hence, dialectal expressions that possess a lexical-semantic significance warrant their introduction into fiction by authors, subsequently leading to their adoption and enrichment of the literary language with universal applicability" [14, p.187]. In contrast to other styles within literary language, the artistic style lacks a distinct stylistic framework, prompting writers to incorporate dialectal words into their works. This underscores the role of the artistic style as an intermediary in the assimilation of dialectical expressions into the literary language. Nevertheless, it is important to note that not all dialecticisms utilized in artistic language find their way into the literary language. Despite their origins in dialect lexicons, the precise attribution of these words to a particular dialect group and their differentiation from colloquial spoken language terms can be

challenging. Consequently, only a specific subset of dialectal elements secures the privilege of incorporation into the literary language. This situation mirrors the relationship of individual neologisms in written language to the literary language, arising as a legitimate consequence of dialect words acquiring a national diversity and unveiling their latent stylistic potential.

Poets and writers originating from regions associated with specific dialects have played a significant role in the expansion and enhancement of the literary language's lexicon through dialectal influences.

Dialectal and accentual words find extensive usage in artistic language, acquiring a stylistic impact that serves as one of the tools for individualizing character speech, crafting distinct personalities, and instilling regional diversity. It is notable that dialect words are more frequently employed in prose compared to poetry. While a poet employs their unique language to describe and exalt various subjects, events, or natural elements, a writer, alongside engaging with imagery in their work, prioritizes the interactions and dialogues among characters. This environment fosters the natural growth of dialectal terms within the language of literary creations. A. Demirchizade articulates this phenomenon: "When it is necessary to infuse an artistic work with a local ambiance and convey the inherent association of a particular image or a set of images with specific regional circumstances, it is deemed suitable to incorporate characteristic dialect words. In general, the language of the artistic work assumes a humorous and entertaining quality". [12, p.89]

S.A. Jafarov concurs with the perspective of A.M. Demirchizade and states: "To depict the existence of a specific region or community in a more authentic and striking way and to breathe life into an individual character within a literary work, the author hailing from that particular locale or associated with the character can extensively employ the distinctive characteristics of the dialect specific to that region" [11, p.80]

Dialect words, which have meanings limited to a specific geographic area, are at times connected to the life and practices of that region, including agricultural aspects, tribal affiliations of the inhabitants, linguistic influences from neighboring areas, and various local events. Naturally, poets and writers residing in these conditions incorporate certain dialect words into their language. This practice not only broadens the individual lexicon of artistic expression but also imparts a spatial quality to the essence of the work and the language used to depict its imagery.

All dialects and accents, which collectively contribute to enriching the literary language of Azerbaijan, hold equal significance. In other words, it is not merely one or two dialect words, but the entirety of dialects and accents within the language that partake in this process, offering vocabulary and expressions to the literary language. Thus, if words and phrases necessary for the literary language, such as those associated with horse breeding, primarily originate from the dialects of Gazakh-Karabakh, while terms related to oil and seafaring are influenced by the Baku dialect, and words and phrases concerning horticulture are influenced by the Guba dialect, these linguistic elements enter our literary

language through three distinct avenues, acquiring their place in the literary domain.

1. Via artistic style. 2. Via scientific style. 3. Via journalistic style.

From this perspective, the dialectal expressions that enhance the composition of contemporary Azerbaijani literary language are more commonly associated with these styles.

Aroy. The word "Aroy" is employed in various dialects and accents, such as the Ganja dialect, the Zangibasar dialect of Western Azerbaijan, and the Goyche dialects, with the meaning of "dirty water left after washing clothes" or simply "dirty water" [11, p.26]. In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language," this word is documented in both "aro" and "aroy" forms as a regional term, and it is defined to signify "dirty water left after washing clothes" or "slops" [6, p.124].

Arsala. The term "Arsala" refers to the lower part of the thigh in meat-eating animals, which is a specific anatomical reference not typically covered by a distinct word in modern Azerbaijani literary language. In the literary language, this part is usually referred to as either the "thigh" or the "lower part of the thigh." Thus, in the Ganja and Gazakh dialects, as well as in the Shamkir dialect, the term "arsala" is used to mean "the lower part of an animal's thigh" [5, p.26]. This dialectal term, as demonstrated in the "Dialectological Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language" from 1964, signifies the "thigh of an animal whose meat is consumed" [3, p.41], providing a unique and region-specific expression for this anatomical feature.

Avazımaq. The term "Avazımaq" is utilized in the Baku, Shamakhi, and Kurdamir dialects, where it is pronounced as "avazımakh." In these dialects, it carries the meanings of "to turn pale," "to fade," and "to wither" [5, p.29]. Interestingly, in the "Dialectological Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language" published in 1964, this word was attributed solely to the Ganja dialect [3, p.15]. Nevertheless, according to the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Azerbaijani language," "avazımaq" is defined as meaning "to turn pale" or "to fade" [6, p.29], suggesting a broader regional usage beyond the Ganja dialect in contemporary Azerbaijani. *Cəlalzadə Dəmirovun avazımış sifətinə baxdı* (S.Rahimov)

Bələn. The term "Bələn" was reflected in the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language" as a dialectism, with the indicated meaning of "field on the mountain" [6, p.245]. It's worth noting that this word can also appear in oral folk literature in the form of "Bələn." *Eyvaz Koroğluynan bərabər qoyunları hayladı, bələndən aşırıldı* ("Koroğlu" epos).

The term "Bələn," as a geographical descriptor, signifies "mountain pass" in the dialects of Ganja, Gazakh, Shamkir, and Tovuz within the Azerbaijani language, as well as in the Karakilsa dialect of Western Azerbaijan [5, p.49]. According to the 1964 edition of the "Dialectological Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language," it was elucidated that the term "bələn" is exclusively employed in the Kazakh dialect, denoting "a small path on the slope of a mountain" [5, p.50]. This

term, "Bələn," may find application as a geographical designation in our literary language.

Təpimək. In the process of drying various wet objects, such as soil or clothes, different levels of dryness can be observed, including complete dryness, partial dryness, slight dryness, and so on. Partial drying, which involves the removal of excess moisture, can be achieved through a term found in certain dialects and accents of the Azerbaijani language known as "təpimək." In specific regions, such as Ganja, Gadabey, Kurdamir, Yevlakh, and Zangilan [5, p.492], as well as in the Chambarak accent of Western Azerbaijan, the term "təpimək" is expressed as "tapimakh" and signifies "dryish."

In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language," "təpimək" is defined as "to dry up, to become dry, to draw water" [10, p.166]. For instance: *Gecə külək əsdiyi üçün yol təpimiş, sahə qurumuşdu* (A.Valiyev).

Indeed, the aforementioned discussion underscores that dialectical elements find their way into the language of artistic works with deliberate intent, often tied to specific stylistic considerations. Poets and writers hailing from various regions of Azerbaijan, possessing a profound familiarity with both the vernacular and its diverse dialects, incorporate dialectal terms and forms into their works for diverse stylistic objectives. Another crucial aspect to bear in mind is that distinct functional styles within the literary language are bound by specific stylistic boundaries, precluding the use of dialectal expressions. However, the realm of artistic style lacks such constraints; it accommodates elements from all styles, including dialectal words. Indeed, there is no category of words within a language that is off-limits to the artistic style. In the realm of artistic expression, all linguistic resources are available for utilization. Within the artistic style, words from diverse backgrounds, whether from the realms of art, professions, or regional dialects, are employed to add distinctive nuances to the stylistic intent or the speech of a character or persona. Each writer, working within the framework of the universal language, finds it essential to draw upon the vocabulary specific to their own cultural and regional context, including dialectal terms. This enriches the literary language with new expressions and phrases. It is imperative for writers as it aligns with the demands of artistic principles, including the differentiation of linguistic styles for characters and the conveyance of ideas in a more figurative manner through the use of abundant synonymous expressions [15, p.72].

The evolution of the contemporary Azerbaijani language, alongside its diverse vocabulary, underscores the significant and irreplaceable role played by dialectal words and accents.

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